

ARTICLE

Understanding Charge Transport in Wavy 2D Covalent Organic Frameworks

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Understanding charge transport in 2D covalent organic frameworks is crucial to increase their performance. Herein a new wavy 2D covalent organic framework has been designed, synthesized and studied to shine light on the structural factors that dominate charge transport.

Introduction

Covalent organic frameworks (COFs) are crystalline solids constituted of covalently linked organic monomers that have become promising materials for several applications, including gas separation and storage, liquid filtration and purification, heterogeneous catalysis and sensing, among others.¹ Among these, two-dimensional covalent organic frameworks (2D COFs) are constituted of crystalline stacks of COF layers. If these layers are formed by π -conjugated monomers, then interlayer π -stacking can open up optimal channels for charge and exciton transport,² enabling new opportunities to design crystalline materials for electronic and optoelectronic applications.³

In this regard, a strategy to increase π -orbital overlap between layers is the use of π -conjugated monomers with a large π -area, such as pyrene, phthalocyanine, tetrathiafulvalene, among many others.⁴ Another strategy that has recently received attention relies on the use of monomers with distinct shapes (bowl-, propeller-, and armchair-shaped precursors)⁵ that favour stacking between 2D COF layers.

Recently, we have introduced distorted polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons as monomers for the synthesis of COFs with unusual architectures and properties.⁶ The use of

2,3,10,11,18,19-hexahydroxy-*cata*-hexabenzocoronene (HBC, Figure 1) –an extended double-bowl shaped distorted polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon– as nodes gave rise to 2D COFs with a wavy chair-like honeycomb lattice. The wavy structure of such 2D COF layers does not interfere with interlayer π -stacking between nodes and linkers but rather guided the stacking of additional layers by concave-convex self-complementarity. In consequence, the wavy 2D COF showed a high degree of crystallinity and anisotropic charge transport properties in the stacking direction similar to those of planar 2D COFs.

An important aspect of this type of wavy 2D COFs that remains to be understood and that have direct implications in the design of COFs with enhanced performance is to identify which units are directly involved in charge transport. For instance, both the HBC nodes and the (pyrene) linkers exhibit large π -areas and a high degree of π -stacking in the resulting wavy 2D COF. To answer this question, we have designed, synthesized and studied, a new wavy 2D COF where the pyrene linkers have been exchanged by phenylene linkers (Marta-COF-2, Figure 2). Studies on Marta-COF-2 reveal that the columnar HBC π -stacks represents the primary pathway for charge transport in this family of wavy 2D COFs.

Figure 1. Crystal structure of HBC.⁶

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Figure 2. a) Schematic reaction for the synthesis of Marta-COF-2. b) Face-on and c) lateral view of the reconstructed monolayer structure of Marta-COF-2. The arrow in b) indicates the direction discussed in the microscopy section.

Results and discussion

Marta-COF-2 was synthesized by solvothermal condensation of 2,3,10,11,18,19-hexahydroxy-cata-hexabenzocoronene (HBC)⁶ and benzene-1,4-diboronic acid (BDBA) in a mixture of 1,4-dioxane and mesitylene (2:1) at 120 °C for 72 hours in a sealed pre-scored ampoule (Figure 2a). Subsequently, the solid was isolated by filtration and washed with anhydrous tetrahydrofuran, acetone and hexane to provide Marta-COF-2 as a yellow solid (90% yield).

The Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectrum of Marta-COF-2 shows bands at 1334 and 1348 cm^{-1} , attributed to strong C-O stretching band distinctive for boronate ester five-membered rings, and the strong attenuation of hydroxyl groups from the precursors (Figure 3a). The Solid-State Cross

Polarization Magic-Angle Spinning (SS CP/MAS) ^{13}C NMR spectrum of Marta-COF-2 (Figure 3b and S1) shows signals that correspond to the phenylene (indicated with circles) and hexabenzocoronene (indicated with stars) residues, while the SS CP-MAS ^{11}B NMR spectrum (Figure 3c) shows a single peak characteristic of a single type of boronate ester linkage.

Marta-COF-2 exhibited clear diffraction peaks in the powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern (Figure 3d-e) with several resolved reflections. The monolayer and crystal structure of Marta-COF-2 were calculated using Density Functional Theory (DFT). Each layer is intrinsically undulated as consequence of the twisted and rigid structure of the HBC node and the alternated disposition of HBC nodes pointing above and below the plane, which gives rise to a chair-like honeycomb lattice (Figure 2b-c). The structural

Figure 3. a) FTIR spectra of BDBA (grey), HBC (red) and Marta-COF-2 (blue). SS CP-MAS b) ^{13}C NMR (partial, circles and stars indicate the peaks that correspond to the phenylene and coronene residues, respectively) and c) ^{11}B NMR of Marta-COF-2. d) Full and e) zoomed experimental and simulated PXRD patterns for the AA packing modes of Marta-COF-2. f) AA stacking modes of Marta-COF-2. g) Nitrogen adsorption and desorption isotherm profiles at 77 K and h) pore size distribution of Marta-COF-2.

concave-convex self-complementarity limits substantially the number of packing arrangements. Two general packing conformations (AA and AB) with three different interlayer stackings were computationally explored, namely, eclipsed, serrated and staircase (Figure 3f). First, the Binding Energy (BE) of the AB stacking modes shows systematically higher energy (~ 100 kcal/mol) than of the AA layer stacking modes (Table S1). Besides, the simulated PXRD diffractograms for AB packing modes do not fit with the experimental ones (Figure S2). Regarding AA stacking modes, the BE of the eclipsed AA stacking (-218 kcal/mol) is higher energy than those of the serrated and staircase AA layer stacking modes, which are

similar in energy (-232 kcal/mol) (Table S1). This is also consistent with the simulated diffractograms of the serrated and staircase AA modes that show a better agreement with the experimental diffractograms than the eclipsed ones (Figure 3d-e), which is also consistent with recent experimental observations by Lotsch and co-workers.⁷ Even if the predicted diffractograms cannot be used to preclude the presence of serrated AA stacking, the predicted PXRD pattern of the staircase AA configuration is more consistent with the experimental one. Pawley refinement (Figure S3) yielded unit cells nearly equivalent to the computational predictions ($a = b = 35.05$ Å, $c = 8.13$ Å, $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ$ and $\gamma = 120^\circ$, $R_p = 3.95\%$ and

$R_{\text{wp}} = 8.11\%$). Additionally, the diffraction patterns at 2.86° , 5.02° , 5.83° , 7.67° , 8.70° , 10.49° , 11.59° , 13.29° were assigned to the (100), ($1\bar{2}0$), (200), (210), (300), (310), (400) and (410) facets, respectively, of the staircase AA packing.

Marta-COF-2 exhibits a reversible type I nitrogen isotherm at 77 K (Figure 2g) with a microporous and mesoporous region. The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) surface area of $1151 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and a pore size of 2.3 nm (Figure 2h) calculated from the isotherm are consistent with theoretical values calculated for Marta-COF-2 in an AA stacking configuration ($1400 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and 2.3 nm, Table S2).

High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) revealed the presence of Marta-COF-2 crystallites that show channel-like features (Figures S4 and S5) that were attributed to the projection of the HBC columns across the zig-zag direction (see arrow in Figure 2b).

The charge transport properties of Marta-COF-2 were assessed by flash-photolysis time-resolved microwave conductivity (FP-TRMC).⁸ FP-TRMC measures the pseudophotococonductivity ($\varphi\sigma\mu$), which is directly related to the minimum or inherent charge carrier mobility of the material. The powders of Marta-COF-2 showed a $\varphi\sigma\mu_{\text{max}}$ value of $0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This $\varphi\sigma\mu_{\text{max}}$ value is in the same range as those generally observed on planar 2D COFs that oscillate between 10^{-5} and $10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.⁹ Most importantly, the $\varphi\sigma\mu_{\text{max}}$ value of Marta-COF-2 is very similar to that observed on the equivalent wavy 2D COF with pyrene linkers ($\varphi\sigma\mu_{\text{max}} = 0.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$).⁶ Taking into account that both wavy 2D COFs show virtually the same chair-like honeycomb 2D structure, the same packing configuration, the same coronene-coronene π -stacking distance (plane-to-centroid = 4\AA) and similar $\varphi\sigma\mu_{\text{max}}$ values, we can safely conclude that the charge carrier mobility is nearly independent of the linker used (phenylene and pyrene) and thus that charge transport takes place preferentially across the channels generated by the stacks of HBC nodes.

Figure 4. $\varphi\sigma\mu$ transients of Marta-COF-2 measured by FP-TRMC.

Conclusions

In summary, we have designed and synthesized a new member of the wavy 2D COF family to shine light on the structural factors that influence their charge transport properties. Marta-COF-2 has been synthesized by condensation between a distorted HBC and BDBA and shows a chair-like honeycomb lattice with AA packing configuration as imposed by the wavy structure. The structure of Marta-COF-2 has been confirmed by a combination of FT-IR, SS NMR, PXRD, gas sorption and HR-TEM. FP-TRMC studies reveal that Marta-COF-2 shows a $\varphi\sigma\mu_{\text{max}}$ value of $0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is very similar to that of a structurally equivalent wavy 2D COF, which varies on the nature of the linkers, indicating that charge transport takes place preferentially across the stacks of HBC nodes. Our results illustrate that twisted aromatics are not only very useful structural units for the synthesis of COFs with unusual structures but also to control charge transport properties.

Author Contributions

M.M.-A. synthesized and characterized (FT-IR, NMR, PXRD) Marta-COF-2 under the supervision of A.M.-A.; K.S. carried out the simulations and constructed the different crystal structures under the supervision of M.M.-F.; C.T.S. and A.N.K. carried out and interpreted the transmission electron microscopy measurements; B.L.-B. and C.M.-G. carried out and interpreted the gas sorption measurements; A.S. carried out the FP-TRMC measurements; M.M.-A. and A.M.-A. wrote the manuscript with the contributions of all authors; A.M.-A. conceived and supervised the study.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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